

The Earthquake Impact on Tourism Industry: The Kos Case

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ABSTRACT

Earthquakes, like other natural disasters, affect the development of the area, the environment, the economy, society and tourism. The objective of this study is to know the impact of earthquakes on tourism. Specifically, the impact of the 2017 earthquake that hit the island of Kos in Greece, affecting local tourism, is studied. The island of Kos is very touristic and the earthquake occurred in July at the height of the tourist season. The main source of income for citizens in this area is based on tourism. During this event, citizens, in their social network accounts, show their concern for the future of tourism in the area. The methodology used is based on the observation of the publications of local users on Twitter and articles in the digital and printed press that address this issue. Data mining from two different sources is performed to understand the general perspective of the media and the vision of citizens. The results show the concern of the natives towards the tourist impact and the attempt to protect and care for the tourists who are in the area during the earthquake.

1. Introduction

Natural disasters are the result of extreme natural, spontaneous, sudden and unpredictable events that require proper management (Becken & Hughey, 2013; Faulkner, 2001; Ritchie, 2008). These events increase vulnerability and affect various economic (Torres, 2004), environmental, social (Gascón, 2005), health, educational, etc. aspects of the community (Mata-Lima et al., 2013). Due to the aspects that characterize them, disasters do not offer the possibility of prior control increasing their impact (Aktas & Gunlu, 2012; Faulkner, 2001). For example, the year 2017 saw a series of hurricanes in the Caribbean and strong earthquakes that resulted in the highest losses ever recorded.

In the case of earthquakes, they directly affect the pillars of sustainable development and have a social impact (humans, animals) (Smith et al., 1996; Lindell et al., 2003; Gleser et al., 2013; Toya et al., 2014), economic (buildings, objects, inflation) (Garay Moena, 2015; Muñoz & Pistelli-Munizaga, 2010; Okuyama et al., 2013) and environmental (terrestrial soil, groundwater) (Arapostathis, 2016; Valdez Zepeda et al., 2018).

From an economic perspective, affected areas suffer extraordinary costs of great impact (International Federation of Red Cross and Red Crescent Societies, 2016; Albornoz Ramirez, 2020; Garay Moena, 2015). In this aspect, tourism as part of the

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economic activity of the area is affected after the natural disaster. In particular, the impact on the tourism sector is demolished from its link with the expectations and confidence of tourists (Bhati et al., 2016; Mazzocchi & Montini, 2001). A natural disaster in the area affects the image of the area and the perception of visitors (Rodríguez-Toubes Muñoz & Álvarez de la Torre, 2013).

At present, natural disasters are becoming more frequent and tourist destinations suffer continuous situations of external crises and vulnerability derived from natural disasters. Such events affect tourism development, especially areas whose tourism activity is dependent on the use of their natural resources (World Tourism Organization, 2003; Beirman, 2020; Ghimire, 2016; Swiss Re Institute Sigma, 2018).

The objective of this study is precisely to know what is the relationship between natural disasters and the tourism sector from the perspective of citizens. With the help of new technologies and in particular of socio-digital networks, users have the possibility to make public their opinion, emotion and concern about the tourist future of the area.

2. Literature Review

Disasters have an immediate and calculable impact, although they also have indirect damages such as economic losses due to the decrease in tourism (Ventura Velázquez et al., 2009). Tourism is a relatively resilient and continuously growing sector (World Tourism Organization, 2019). This phenomenon accelerated the economic development of many areas worldwide, including poor or developing countries.

However, the tourism sector has a fragile activity that leads to high vulnerability (Becken et al., 2015; Sharpley, 2005). External factors from different sectors, disasters, crises, political instability etc. immediately affect tourism in the area, since disasters have the power to persuade visitors to travel to the affected destinations, and it is difficult to properly manage the crisis in the sector (Bhati et al., 2016; Sausmarez, 2004; Huang & Min; 2002; Goeldner et al., 2011; Shondell Miller, 2008). Although, the nature and extent of the impacts depend on the origin, magnitude of the disaster and the resilience of the affected system (OECD, 2014).

Disasters can cause significant physical damage to the offer of tourism services (Shaw et al., 2012). Critical infrastructures such as airports, ports, electricity, land transport, etc. are often damaged and limit the supply of services (Ghobarah et al., 2006; Parajuli & Haynes, 2006). In addition, the main tourist attractions can be damaged limiting the future tourist possibilities of the area, making it impossible to restore the sector (Becken, 2015).

The problems of managing the impact of a disaster from the tourism sector emerge from their very nature. Tourism is designed to create positive feelings and it is not typical of the sector to design a plan for disaster management (Herrero, 1998). This lack of planning affects management in times of crisis, making the tourism sector more vulnerable to any threat. Therefore, establishing prevention plans for

these risks should be an integral component of the tourism sector (Shakeela & Becken, 2015). Other aspects to take into account in relation to the vulnerability of the tourism sector is that it is affected by disasters in other areas and sectors (Beirman, 2020). Tourism is based on the ability of people from other states to enjoy their free time. Therefore, a disaster suffered in another country affects its economy by exerting a domino effect on the tourist country and other sectors (Beirman, 2020; Ritchie, 2004).

In the short term, the consequences in the tourism sector are derived from the decrease in the arrival of tourists, cancellation of reservations, loss of confidence, or by the efforts related to the return of the destination or business to normality (Bhati et al., 2016; Mazzocchi & Montini, 2001; Sharpley, 2005; Sönmez et al., 1999). Visualizing the situation with a longer-term approach identifies problems related to the threat of continued activity of tourism companies and damage to the image of the area as a safe and relaxing destination (Sönmez et al., 1999). Safety aspects are important to maintain an attractive image as a tourist destination that affect the decisions of visitors leading to the need for a quick and adequate restoration (Sharifpour et al., 2014; Trumbo et al., 2016; Williams & Baláž, 2015).

It is understood that the repercussions of a disaster directly affect tourism in an area as well as travel to and from that area (Jin et al., 2019; Ruan et al., 2017). These repercussions affect citizens who come to socio-digital networks to share their feelings, concerns, information, opinions, etc. (Morales et al., 2018). Socio-digital networks are tools that promote the participation and relief of users. Therefore, the observation of the publications present in the socio-digital networks show the atmosphere of the community in “real time” and the concerns of the users regarding the situation generated (Noris & Jones, 2005: 139; Scollon, 2001: 8-9).

However, extracting the information from all the related publications issued in all the socio-digital networks is incomprehensible. However, the press reflects the real and momentary situation of what has been experienced since what was exposed in the socio-digital networks. The press includes the opinion of users, present in the socio-digital networks, on the situation and the impact of the event on the tourism sector. The information included in the press reflects all the publications of the users.

3. Methodology

3.1. Objective

The objective of this work is to know the impact of natural disasters on tourism from the perception of the natives reflected in the socio-digital networks. The seismic event in July 2017 with the epicenter of the island of Kos was an interesting situation to assess the damage and the effects of the event on tourism on the island in the short term. Users made posts on socio-digital networks that show such an impact.

3.2. Tools

In the present study, the following sources of data extraction are chosen:

- Press articles (digital and printed) on the mentions of users in socio-digital networks related to the impact of the event on the tourism sector. The selection of this source of information is due to the possibility of obtaining through the articles.
- Publications made on Twitter. The selection from Twitter is due to its popularity during seismic events, the possibility of public debates without a previous link and its popularity in a normal situation (Allier Montaño, 2018; Arapostathis, 2016; IAB Spain, 2017; 2018; Salgado Andrade, 2018).

3.3. Design and procedure

To understand these aspects, it is necessary to have the support of different research methods by extracting data from different sources and reaching an observation from different angles (Denzin, 1978). Therefore, the extraction of data is chosen by the socio-digital network of Twitter, where users make publications about the situation of the tourism industry. From this source, a data extraction is carried out during the days 21 and 22 July 2017. The publications studied are those that contain the #σεισμός, #σεισμος, #seismos, #sismos (earthquake), #Κως, #Kos, #Kws (Kos), and are present on the network during the indicated dates. Different types of typing of the same word are chosen in the search tools. This is because in networks it is common to use the Latin alphabet or write without accents. In the case of writing with the Latin alphabet, different forms of writing are offered, respecting more or less the graphic characteristics of the Greek alphabet.

On the other hand, a compilation of the digital press and printing press is made. In this way, social perception is understood in the set of socio-digital networks and not only in Twitter. The selected press articles come from the local press (state and island). The search was carried out in the Google search engine with the help of the keywords: social network - σεισμος - κω - 2017 - 21/07/2017. All links were opened and selected manually. The articles included were all of them that made any mention of the role that socio-digital networks had in the management of the earthquake.

3.4. Data analysis

Data analysis is presented in table format. Two tables are presented where the first includes the data extracted from the publications on Twitter, while the second table includes the information that the press. Table 1 shows what is included in Twitter posts that reflect the opinions, emotions and criticisms of users. This table presents the frequency of these publications on the first two days of the disaster as well as the difference and average frequency between these days. Table 2 includes the publications in the networks related to the impact of the event on tourism. This table presents the characteristics and general notions of all the publications related to tourism, during the earthquake, in the socio-digital networks. In this way, the general environment of the users can be understood.

4. Results and Discussion

On 27/07/2017 took place in Greece, and specifically in the Aegean Sea, an earthquake of magnitude 6.7 (Mw) and depth 10km. The worst affected area was the island of Kos, but damage was recorded in several places in Greece and Turkey. The quake struck early on a Friday and was followed by a magnitude 5.1 earthquake. This seismic event caused a lot of damage to infrastructure while the invasion of salt water due to the tsunami altered the composition of the land affecting land and crops.

Both the disaster itself, due to the fear and chaos it generates, and the destruction of infrastructure negatively affect tourism. This situation led to the precipitous end of the tourist season, with great economic consequences since the main source of income on the island is tourism.

The table that follows presents the frequency of publications on Twitter that mention aspects related to the situation of tourism in the area after the seismic event.

Table 1. Frequency of publications on tourism

Publications in Twitter	21/07	22/07	Difference	Average
Concern about tourism	15.70%	26.22%	10.52%	20.96%

Source: Author's elaboration

During 21/07 most of the publications are related to the physical and emotional situation of tourists. Due to the importance of the tourism sector and the date on which the earthquake happens, the impact on the sector is great and therefore, it is present in the publications of the networks. After the first day, and the first impact, the mention of tourist aspects in the publications focuses more on the concern about the future of tourism and the economic impact on the area.

The main concerns of the users present in the socio-digital networks during both days studied about tourism are related to:

The situation of the future of tourism: Users show their concern about the economic impact of the event. The earthquake took place in the middle of the tourist season leading to its precipitous end. In addition, due to the structured damage, users show their concern about the impact of the event on the tourist season of the following year. To this situation is added the disinterest of the agents worries the users and the fear for the future increases the stress and concern of those affected.

The emotional and physical state of tourists: During the first day the publications show greater attention to the situation of the victims and the state of the injured. After the seismic event, two tourists lost their lives inside the rubble while inside a bar. In addition, many tourists were injured and others were in a state of panic. The emotional situation of tourists was quite critical according to user posts. This is because the greatest impact of the event occurred in the tourist area of the island, due to the age of the buildings, and that many of them had not experienced another similar situation.

Special services for the support of tourists: Through publications on the social network's users, hoteliers and simple citizens, informed those interested where to stay and receive help. Hotels, cafes and restaurants offered free services to support tourists who were on the island.

Ending with the mentions made in the Twitter socio-digital network, we continue with the analysis of the articles of the printing and digital press exposed in the following table. The articles are presented alphabetically.

Table 2. Press articles included

Article	Type of press	Publication date
Demetis (2017)	Digital	21/07/2017
CNN (2017)	Digital	21/07/2017
Kokkinidis (2017)	Digital	21/07/02017
Ieromnimon (2017)	Digital	21/07/2017
Iliadi (2017)	Digital	21/07/2017
Newsbomb (2017)	Digital	21/07/2017
Proto Thema (2017)	Imprenta	21/07/2017

Source: Author's elaboration

In the articles of the press the content of the publications presents in the networks related to tourism in the area is collected. In these, users show, mainly, their concern about tourists and their well-being. Due to the large number of foreign tourists on the island, this seismic event became the first news in the British media (Demetis, 2017).

The area most affected by the earthquake was the old part containing old buildings that were not built according to current standards (CNN, 2017; Iliadi, 2017). This area is where most of the bars and cafes are located, where tourists and natives meet at the time of the earthquake. It was in this area where two tourists died on the spot and many were injured, due to the collapse of the roof in an establishment (CNN, 2017; Ieromnimon, 2017; Iliadi, 2017; Kokkinidis, 2017; Newsbomb, 2017; Proto Thema, 2017). Meanwhile, the rest of the people who were in that establishment or in the nearby area remained in a state of shock (CNN, 2017; Demetis, 2017; Iliadi, 2017; Kokkinidis, 2017; Newsbomb, 2017). Frightened tourists without knowing how to react, without experience in this type of natural events tried to get to safety while they were looking for their companions and inform their own that they were well (CNN; 2017; Ieromnimon, 2017). The natives were trying to help them, but they were in shock (Ieromnimon, 2017).

However, infrastructure damage was not limited in the downtown area and many hotels had structural damage (CNN, 2017; Newsbomb, 2017). Due to the situation, many of the guests were unable to stay in the establishments and had to sleep outside. During the night they camped next to hotels and the airport while hospitality workers offered everything they needed (Demesis, 2017; Ieromnimon, 2017).

However, not all structural damage was directly due to the quake. After the main seismic strike, a tsunami hit the island's harbor causing extensive structural damage throughout the port area (CNN; 2017; Iliadi, 2017; Kokkinidis, 2017; Newsbomb, 2017). These damages were useless and no ship could reach or leave it (Demesis, 2017; Proto Thema, 2017). Due to the situation many ships, with a large number of tourists, could not disembark on the island, while tourists who wanted to continue their scheduled trip were stuck in port (Demesis, 2017; CNN, 2017; Iliadi, 2017; Newsbomb, 2017). However, the island's airport continued with its normal operation, after verifying that tourists and natives could make safe use of it (Demesis, 2017; Iliadi, 2017; Newsbomb, 2017).

Due to the situation, users showed concern about tourism in economic aspects (Proto Thema, 2017). The inhabitants of the island rely on tourism to live and the earthquake threatens the tourist season. Apart from the vital structures, there were many cultural, archaeological and religious buildings among which they presented great structural damage (Proto Thema, 2017). Such an impact affects the tourist future of the area and worries the natives.

5. Conclusion

Socio-digital networks reflect the situation and concerns of users about local and international issues that affect them. In the case studied, after a seismic blow, local users went to the networks to share what happened and the impact of the earthquake on tourism in the area, I feel the main source of income for the natives. The socio-digital networks and the press, which compiles the publications, reflect the situation from the publications of the citizens.

This study shows the impact of a disastrous event on the tourism sector from different aspects. Users show greater concern about the immediate impact reflecting the magnitude of the disaster, the level of vulnerability of the area and the responsiveness of the agents. The main focus of the publications is the number of dead and injured, of which most are tourists. This fact affects tourism in the short and long term since it relates the image of the island with instability and danger. Tourists prefer quiet and relaxing places to spend their free time avoiding conflicting and dangerous sites.

However, the event has an impact on infrastructures and buildings in the area that affect local tourism from different perspectives. Critical infrastructure, such as damage to the port, makes it impossible for new tourists to arrive and those who are already on the island to leave, making journeys difficult. A slow repair of port damage can affect tourism in the long run. In addition, damage to cultural buildings affects tourism in the short and long term. Buildings of cultural, religious and archaeological value are an attraction for tourists and the loss of these affects the image, possibilities and tourist interest.

Finally, this study concludes that seismic events, and natural disasters in general, affect the tourism industry of an area in the short and long term. This study

shows how this impact is reflected through the socio-digital networks used by the users themselves who show their concern about the tourism future of the area.

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